

TABLE 1*

Chemical shift δ	No. of protons	Splitting pattern	Assignment of protons
1.38	6	s	2-ter. CH_3
1.83	2	t (J = 6 Hz)	$-CH_2$ (Chroman)
2.71	2	t	$-CH_2$ (Chroman)
3.11	4	s (broad)	$-C-CH_2-CH_2$ -aryl O
5.16	1	s	C_5-OH (disappears on D_2O exchange).
7.11	1	s	aromatic (C_6-H)
7.25	5	s	aromatic (B ring)
13.83	1	s	C_2-OH (disappears on D_2O exchange).

* Taken in $CDCl_3$ with TMS as internal standard. Signals are denoted in the usual way: s = singlet; t = triplet.

1

V

Flemichapparin-A (I), on boiling with acetic acid or aqueous NaOH for 6 hr. in N_2 atmosphere, afforded an isomeric product, $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$, m.p. $161^\circ-162^\circ$, in poor yield (10-15%). The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 256 (log ϵ 4.33), 310 (log ϵ 3.66) and 350 nm (log ϵ 3.66)] is compatible with a flavanone structure (V) as the latter exhibits triple maxima (with bathochromic shifts of the maxima) very similar to the UV spectra of 6:7:3':4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone⁴ and 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy-flavanone⁵. The 60 MHz NMR spectrum (in $CDCl_3$) also suggests a flavanone structure (V) for this transformation product. The chromene ring is defined by the appearance of two olefinic protons at δ 6.6 and δ 5.56 δ , each appearing as a doublet (J = 10Hz) and two ter. methyls at δ 1.5 δ as a 6H-singlet. The aromatic protons (B ring) signal around δ 7.43 as a multiplet and the phenolic $-OH$ as a singlet at δ 5.26 (disappears on D_2O exchange). The C-5 proton appears as a singlet at δ 7.30 δ . The occurrence of a rough triplet around δ 2.93 δ and an unresolved quartet around δ 5.50 δ suggests that these

signals are most probably due to the C-3 and C-2 protons^{5,6} of the flavanone derivative (V). Further studies on the chemistry of (I) are underway.

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Application of Viscosity Equations for the System : Barium Soap-Water and Propanol-1

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IN the previous communications^{1,2} the viscosity of barium soaps (valerate and caproate) solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions has been studied. In the present work, an attempt has been made to apply the various viscosity equations^{4,5} for the above system with a view to find out the nature of micelles formed in soap solutions in mixed solvents.

Experimental

The preparation of the soaps and measurements of the viscosity has been described in the previous communications^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Several equations³⁻⁵ have been put forward for testing the viscosity of electrolytes and non-electrolytes solutions⁶. However, the viscosity of Barium soap solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions has been satisfactorily represented in the wide range of concentrations by equations :

$$\eta_{\text{and}} : \frac{1}{C} = \frac{(0.921)^{-1}}{V} \frac{1}{\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}} + Q\bar{V} \dots (1)$$

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TABLE I(A). THE VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS FOR BARIUM VALERATE

Volume % of propanol-1	Tested concn. limit in moles/litre	Valid Zones in moles/litre	\bar{V}	Q	M	K'
10	0.006—0.425	0.065—0.425	0.31	-1.59	1.16	0.04
20	0.006—0.505	0.065—0.425	0.35	0.57	1.26	0.04
30	0.006—0.425	0.065—0.425	0.33	0.60	1.21	0.04
40	0.006—0.585	0.065—0.585	0.39	0.52	1.24	0.05
50	0.006—0.425	0.065—0.425	0.31	0.64	1.19	0.05
60	0.006—0.345	0.065—0.345	0.39	1.04	1.23	0.05
70	0.006—0.265	0.065—0.265	0.41	1.00	1.18	0.04

TABLE I(B). THE VALUES OF THE PARAMETERS FOR BARIUM CAPROATE

Volume % propanol-1	Tested concn. limit in moles/litre	Valid Zones in moles/litre	\bar{V}	Q	M	K'
10	0.006—0.105	0.025—0.105	0.32	-4.65	1.06	0.001
20	0.006—0.105	0.025—0.105	0.55	5.45	1.09	0.002
30	0.006—0.085	0.025—0.085	0.55	6.33	1.09	0.002
40	0.006—0.065	0.025—0.065	0.55	6.33	1.09	0.004
50	0.006—0.065	0.025—0.065	0.51	3.95	1.05	0.004
60	0.006—0.045	0.025—0.045	0.42	3.62	1.05	0.003

where Q and \bar{V} are the interaction coefficient and molar volume of the solute in litre mole⁻¹ and C is the concentration of the solute in moles litre⁻¹.

$$\text{Moulik: } \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right)^2 = M + K'C^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Where M and K' are constants.

$$\text{Plots of } \frac{1}{C} \text{ Vs. } \frac{1}{\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}}$$

for equation (1) and $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ Vs. C^2 for equation (2) have been made and linearity of these results has been tested. It has been observed that these equations hold good for the data only in a limited range of concentration which has been given in the Tables I(A) and I(B). The tables reveal that the equations are valid only in the concentration range above C.M.C. (CMC for valerate and caproate are 0.025M and 0.0125 M, respectively) for barium soap solutions. Thus, these equations have pointed out the lower concentration limit below which the existence of CMC is possible.

The values of molar volume, \bar{V} , have been calculated from the slopes

$$\left(= \frac{\bar{V}}{0.921} \right) \text{ of the plot of } \frac{1}{C} \text{ Vs. } \frac{1}{\log \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}}$$

and results are given in the tables I(A) and I(B).

It has been observed that the values of \bar{V} remain almost constant with the increase in alcohol concentration below 50% and show change above it which suggests that a change in behaviour occurs at about 50% propanol-1 concentration. The values of \bar{V} , for caproate are higher than the corresponding values of valerate at different compositions of solvents and this may be due to greater tendency of aggregates to form in caproate than in valerate.

The interaction coefficient, Q , have been calculated from the intercept ($= Q\bar{V}$) and are given in the Tables I(A) and I(B). The values show a change at about 50% concentration of propanol-1, which again supports the result of \bar{V} . It is also noted that the value of Q for caproate are higher than corresponding values of valerate at different mixtures of the solvent.

In order to compare the applicability of both the equations the constants K' and M have been calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of the $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ Vs. C^2 and the results are given in the Tables I(A) and I(B). The nature of their variation also follow the order of both \bar{V} and Q .

It may be pointed out that the various values of \bar{V} , Q , M and K' show deviations for 10% propanol-1 which has also been observed in other measurements^{1,2}.

Both the equations have revealed that the change in the nature of micelles takes place at about 50% propanol-1 concentration which has also been obtained from conductivity and surface tension⁷ results. The Vand's equation contains perfectly defined parameter \bar{V} and the interaction coefficient, Q is only approximately obtained⁸. It appears that most probably Q is a specific property of a solute; it is not the general property⁶. It should be mentioned that the parameters M and K' of equation (2) are not yet defined. Only the values obtained has confirmed the result that the change in the nature of the micelles occurs at about 50% propanol-1.

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